

Environmental Data

a key resource

NERC's Environmental Data

a key resource

As the lead body in the UK for research, survey, monitoring and training in the environmental sciences, the Natural Environment Research Council (NERC) has two key resources: its expert work force and its scientific data holdings. Data are the lifeblood of scientific research, and NERC plays a key rôle in environmental data management, with an international reputation in the field.

Almost all environmental data are unique in the time of sampling, and changing conditions may make re-collection impossible. Many of NERC's datasets are therefore irreplaceable. Series of measurements accumulated over decades, and historical records dating back to the 19th century are crucial evidence about our environment today; tracing its past development helps to predict future changes. It was through records collected over thirty

years that NERC scientists first identified the hole in the ozone layer. NERC's data archives will doubtless hold the key to new environmental questions as yet unasked.

Environmental data relate to such a wide variety of scientific disciplines that responsibility for them is best

distributed amongst specialists with appropriate expertise. The responsibility for NERC's data has therefore been divided on discipline-related lines between specialist Data Centres (see box) liaising closely together so that NERC's data resource is managed as a coherent whole. Full details of the Data Centres are given at the back of this document.

NERC's Data Policy

NERC's data policy (available on request) has been formulated to be consistent both with legal frameworks such as the Environmental Information Regulations and contractual arrangements with other bodies whereby, for example, NERC holds their data on a confidential basis without owning the intellectual property rights. Key aspects of the policy include:

- NERC aims to realise the value of its data resource by using it to further scientific understanding, create wealth and improve the quality of life. This can be done in a variety of ways including: using datasets within NERC's own institutes; giving, exchanging or licensing/selling them to other scientific researchers; or licensing/selling them to commercial organisations which will themselves create wealth. Data are thus a potentially tradeable asset.
- Teams and individuals who have collected datasets are allowed a reasonable period of exclusive use during which to analyse them and publish results.
- Charges for data are dependent on the uses to which the data will be put, with any consequent restrictions being specified in formal licence agreements. Revenue from commercial applications of NERC's data contributes towards the substantial costs of collection and long term data management. By contrast, NERC wishes to ensure inexpensive access to its holdings by bona fide academic researchers; ie those whose research is solely to advance knowledge and not for commercial gain, and who will publish their results in the open

NERC DATA CENTRES

The NERC Designated Data Centres have overall responsibility for all NERC data, the divisions between them being based on scientific discipline or geography as follows:

Oceanographic data

British Oceanographic Data Centre BODC

Atmospheric data

British Atmospheric Data Centre BADC

Earth sciences data

National Geosciences Information Service NGIS

Hydrological data

National Water Archive NWA

Terrestrial/freshwater ecological data

Environmental Information Centre EIC

NERC data collected in the Antarctic

Antarctic Environmental Data Centre AEDC

Data not specific to a discipline, eg remotely sensed imagery from satellites and aircraft

NERC Scientific Services Data Centre NSSDC

literature. According to circumstances, data are supplied to such users either wholly free of charge, for a nominal handling fee, or at an appropriately discounted rate.

Accessing and Using NERC Data

An overview of the Data Centres and their holdings is given in the main sections of the NERC Data Holdings Catalogue and on the World Wide Web. Some NERC data are routinely published in summary form, eg in the annual Hydrological Data UK Yearbooks from the National Water Archive. Digital data in the form of standard products/packages are generally supplied on diskette or CD-ROM. Data supplied in response to specific requests are made available on a variety of modern computer compatible media. An increasing number of NERC datasets are being made available via the World Wide Web.

A range of software tools is required to process such a diversity of data. NERC scientists themselves employ a variety of proprietary software products, both specialist and general purpose - eg geographical information systems. NERC itself supplies software packages for storage, manipulation and analysis of environmental data in specialist application areas. Such packages can be used with data from both NERC and other sources.

Further information, generally including more detailed catalogues, can be obtained from the Data Centres' home pages on the World Wide Web. These are accessible from NERC's home page URL <http://www.nerc.ac.uk/>

Some of the Data Centres also supply more sophisticated catalogue products, typically for use on personal computers, to help enquirers locate the data they need. Some of NERC's substantial data products are supplied as packages which come complete with the software necessary to search and browse them.

Enquiries or requests for specific datasets should be sent directly to the Data Centres via e-mail, telephone, fax or mail.

NERC Data

Holdings

Catalogue

March 1997

BRITISH OCEANOGRAPHIC DATA CENTRE (BODC)

BODC is hosted by the Proudman Oceanographic Laboratory at Bidston Observatory on Merseyside, a component institute of NERC's Centre for Coastal and Marine Sciences. In addition to its role as NERC's Designated Data Centre for marine data, BODC is part of an international network of national oceanographic data centres collaborating under the auspices of the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) of UNESCO. It has an international reputation for managing data from large scale, multi-disciplinary oceanographic field experiments and for developing innovative marine data products. BODC is responsible for maintaining the General Bathymetric Chart of the Oceans (GEBCO) on behalf of the IOC and the International Hydrographic Organization (IHO).

DIGITAL DATA PRODUCTS PUBLISHED BY BODC

The GEBCO Digital Atlas **CD ROM**

This digital atlas represents the first seamless, high quality, digital bathymetric contour chart of the world's oceans. Published in vector form, it is accompanied by a high resolution world coastline and a geographically referenced set of undersea feature names. It is supplied with an IBM-compatible PC software package which allows the atlas contents to be viewed interactively and for selected extracts to be exported into the user's own applications. A coloured brochure is available on request.

BOFS North Atlantic Project Data Set **CD ROM**

The Biogeochemical Ocean Flux Study (BOFS) was a NERC Community Research Project to study the role of the oceans in the global cycling of carbon. The field programme comprised 11 deep sea cruises between May 1989 and July 1991 and involved over 100 scientists and technicians from 11 universities and 4 NERC laboratories. In addition to physical oceanographic data, a wide range of biological and chemical measurements were also collected from in-situ sensors, water samples, net hauls, sediment traps, and cores. The CD-ROM contains the final project data set encompassing 98% of the data collected.

NERC North Sea Project Data Set **CD ROM**

The North Sea Project undertook a concerted multidisciplinary study of circulation, transport and production in the southern North Sea. During the main data collection period (August 1988 - October 1989) survey cruises were repeated monthly

following the same 1800 nautical mile track. These were interspersed with process study cruises investigating some particular aspect of the dynamics of the North Sea. Follow-up cruises were undertaken during the next 12 months. The CD-ROM contains the final project dataset covering 98% of the data collected over the 38 cruises of the field programme.

UKDMAP: The UK Digital Marine Atlas **diskette**

UKDMAP is a unique reference work on the seas around the British Isles which is of interest to schools, research workers, planners and engineers alike. It covers a variety of themes, including: general reference; marine geology and geomorphology; marine and coastal parks; reserves and protected areas; marine and coastal conservation in Great Britain; sea birds; sea mammals; marine biology; currents; tides and surges; winds; waves and weather; sea water temperature; chemical distributions; exploitation of the marine environment; fishing areas; fish spawning areas; and BODC data catalogues.

While not a full geographic information system, the atlas is a versatile tool. Users can select and display any of 463 coloured charts, with facilities including zoom, overlay, viewing associated text, querying on specific locations and output of associated graphical or textual information. It runs on a suitably configured IBM PC or compatible. A coloured brochure is available on request.

GLOSS Station Handbook: Global Sea Level Observing System **CD ROM**

This is a comprehensive database of information about the 308 tide gauge stations that currently make up the IOC's GLOSS network. In addition there is a complete listing of the 42 500 station years of monthly mean sea level data held by the Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level as of June 1996 and covering 1750 stations worldwide. The package includes a simple user interface and viewable copies of the IOC's manuals on sea level measurement and interpretation.

IOC Current Meter Inventory **diskette**

The Inventory is maintained by BODC on behalf of the IOC and includes references to over 29 000 current meter series collected by laboratories in Australia, Belgium, Canada, Chile, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Russia, Spain, Sweden, UK and USA. A user friendly, PC based, software package enables entries to be retrieved selectively and browsed on screen, viewed on a map or listed to a file or printer.

European Directory of Marine Environmental Data (EDMED) *World Wide Web*

With funding from the EU Marine Science and Technology Programme, BODC has been responsible for designing and compiling an extensive directory of the marine environmental datasets held within the Member States of the EU. The directory contains descriptions of over 2000 data sets from almost 500 laboratories in Belgium, Denmark, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Netherlands, Spain, Portugal and the UK. It is directly accessible over the World Wide Web

(URL=<http://www.nbi.ac.uk/bodc/edmed.html>) with an inbuilt search engine for selecting data set descriptions by geographic area, data type or source laboratory.

BODC DATA HOLDINGS

BODC holds an extensive range of data sets which can be made available to users. These range from national holdings of tide gauge data, CTD data, instrumentally collected wave data, moored current meter data and met ocean data from buoys, weatherships and oil rigs to project orientated datasets of physical, biological and chemical data.

Detailed descriptions of these data sets may be found via the World Wide Web through BODC's Home Page. Examples of major data sets assembled and maintained by BODC include:

- ④ North Sea Project Data Set (1988-90)
- ④ BOFS North Atlantic Data Set (1989-91)
- ④ BOFS Southern Oceans Data Set (1992)
- ④ PRIME Arabesque Indian Ocean Data Set (1994)
- ④ PRIME Mesocosm Experiment & North Atlantic Cruise Data Set (1995-96)
- ④ Land Ocean Interaction Study (LOIS) marine data set (1992-)
- ④ World Ocean Circulation Experiment (WOCE) Sea Level Data Set
- ④ UK contribution to the World Ocean Circulation Experiment (WOCE) (1991-)
- ④ Ocean Margin Exchange (OMEX) Project Data Set (1993-)
- ④ Joint Air-Sea Interaction (JASIN) Project Data Set (1978)
- ④ Mediterranean-Alpine Experiment (MEDALPEX) Sea Level Data Set (1981-82)
- ④ UK Cruise Summary Reports (1970-)
- ④ UK National Databank of Coastal Tide Gauge Data (1842-)
- ④ UK National Databank of Moored Current Meter Data (1967-)
- ④ UK National Databank of CTD STD profiles (1975-)

- ④ UK classical hydrographic station data set (1893-)
- ④ UK National Databank of Wave Data (Short term statistics) (1955-)
- ④ One-dimensional Wave Spectra collected by UK Laboratories (1976-)
- ④ UK Offshore Operators Association (UKOOA) Met Ocean Data Set (1973-88)
- ④ Sea Rover/SeaSoar basin scale traverses of the North Atlantic (1981-91)
- ④ POL Databank of Bottom Pressure Recorder Data (1970-83)
- ④ NW European Shelf Tidal Current Constituent Data Bank (1970-88)
- ④ North Sea Wave Model (NORSWAM) Input Data Set (1966-76)
- ④ Bristol Channel Suspended Sediments Data Bank (1974-78)
- ④ North Atlantic Ocean Weather Ship (OWS) Hydrocast Data (1910-90)

CURRENT BODC ACTIVITIES

- ④ Project Data Centre for:
 - a) Marine component of NERC's Land Ocean Interaction Study (LOIS)
 - b) EU Ocean Margin Exchange (OMEX) project
 - c) UK component of the Joint Global Ocean Flux Study (JGOFS)
 - d) NERC Plankton Reactivity in the Marine Environment (PRIME) project
 - e) UK component of World Ocean Circulation Experiment (WOCE)
- ④ WOCE Data Assembly Centre for Sea Level Data
- ④ Data Centre for the UK National Tide Gauge Network
- ④ UK Digital Marine Atlas Project
- ④ IOC/IHO General Bathymetric Chart of the Oceans
- ④ EU European Directory of Marine Environmental Data

BODC CONTACTS

BODC Enquiries Officer
British Oceanographic Data Centre
Proudman Oceanographic Laboratory
Bidston Observatory
Birkenhead, Merseyside L43 7RA
United Kingdom

Telephone: +44 (0) 151 653 8633

Fax: +44 (0) 151 652 3950

e-mail: bodcmail@pol.ac.uk

Home page:

<http://www.nbi.ac.uk/bodc/bodcmain.html>

BRITISH ATMOSPHERIC DATA CENTRE (BADC)

The British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC) is the Natural Environment Research Council's (NERC) Designated Data Centre for the Atmospheric Sciences. It is sited at the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL) in Oxfordshire, part of the Central Laboratory of the Research Councils (CLRC). The BADC has substantial data holdings and also provides links to information and data held by other data centres.

BADC DATA HOLDINGS

The BADC holds data on the atmosphere and related data sets. The data are from satellite instruments, computer models, ground-based, aircraft and balloon-borne instruments.

The data held by BADC fall naturally into three types:

- ◆ data sets produced by NERC funded programmes eg MST radar, ACSOE, ISAMS.
- ◆ 3rd party data sets required by a broad section of the research community eg meteorological data from the UK Meteorological Office and the European Centre for Medium Range Forecasting (ECMWF).
- ◆ 3rd party data sets available on CD-ROM for browsing.

BADC SATELLITE DATA SETS

The BADC has substantial data holdings of global atmospheric satellite data from both UK and third party instruments. These include temperature, methane and nitrous oxide measurements from early instruments such as the Oxford Stratosphere and Mesosphere Sounder (SAMS) which flew on board the NIMBUS 7 satellite (1978 - 83) through to the more recent atmospheric constituent data relevant to stratospheric ozone depletion measured by instruments on board the Upper Atmosphere Research Satellite (UARS). These include temperature, ozone, water vapour, chlorine monoxide, CFCs, aerosol extinction, methane, nitrous oxide, hydrogen chloride, hydrogen fluoride and nitrogen dioxide data from the Improved Stratosphere and Mesosphere Sounder (ISAMS), the Microwave Limb Sounder (MLS) and the Halogen Occultation Experiment (HALOE). Third party data, such as the global ozone measurements from the NASA Total Ozone Mapping Spectrometer (TOMS) are also acquired and updated on a daily basis to enable users to follow the evolution of the Ozone Hole.

THE NERC - UKMO DATA AGREEMENT

A formal agreement has been reached between NERC and the UK Meteorological Office (UKMO) in which requests for meteorological data for NERC funded atmospheric research are coordinated by the BADC. This arrangement is designed to increase efficiency and avoid duplicate requests. Where there is sufficient demand, the BADC provides a service for the bulk acquisition and distribution of data. Current examples of these include radiosonde, climate station and ECMWF model data sets, described in more detail in the next sections.

BADC RADIOSONDE AND SYNOPTIC STATION DATA

The BADC has acquired radiosonde ascents from the UKMO from over 150 sites throughout Europe. The data consist of temperature, wind and humidity observations every six hours. The database extends from 1990 to the present and is updated on a regular basis. In addition, data from the dense network of synoptic and climate stations have been acquired and an extensive data service is under development for these popular data.

BADC METEOROLOGICAL MODEL DATA

Under the NERC-UKMO Data Agreement the BADC has acquired extensive meteorological analyses from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasting (ECMWF). These include high resolution spectral and gridded temperature and wind data from the ECMWF Re-Analysis (ERA) project in which model analyses were generated for the period 1979-1994 using the same version of the model, thus producing a coherent time-series of considerable value for climate studies. More recent data from the operational analyses are also acquired and updated regularly. The data include 2.5 degree gridded temperatures, winds, humidity and a range of surface parameters. Using wind data from ECMWF, series of 5-day back trajectories from a dense grid of points over the UK and Atlantic are also made available.

ACCESS TO BADC DATA HOLDINGS

All BADC data sets are held on-line. Extensive information on the BADC data sets is available through the BADC World Wide Web interface (WWW). The BADC web address is <http://www.badc.rl.ac.uk/>. In many cases this is also the route to the data themselves. However, some have restrictions on their access. For example, all users of meteorological data sets supplied through the UK Meteorological Office must sign a Data Protocol before gaining access to the data. For this reason, not all of the BADC data sets are available

through the WWW interface. In these cases, users are provided with an account on the BADC computer once they have signed the Protocol and the data are then accessed via ftp.

BADC data sets are catalogued. The catalogue can be searched by keyword or categories eg meteorology, climate, dynamics, chemistry etc.

Software is provided to assist in the manipulation of the data and extensive information is provided on the data collection procedures, formats, data quality, contact names and references to journal papers. Other specialist services include the development of value added data products such as averaged and gridded data and the generation of video sequencing of data for viewing large data sets over long periods. For example, a video tape of the entire sequence of TOMS total ozone maps is available.

BADC WWW Links

The BADC WWW service also provides an excellent collection of links to sites running WWW servers offering data and information relevant to the atmospheric sciences (<http://www.badc.rl.ac.uk/>). The collection of links can be searched by keyword or browsed by category. There are also links to web search facilities and public domain software archives.

CURRENT BADC DATA SETS

All the data sets currently held by the BADC are listed below. The WWW catalogue entry indicates any access restrictions, whether the dataset is available on line, and on what other media, if any, it can be supplied. A full description is provided as illustrated below.

The full list of data sets is as follows:

- AAOE: Airborne Antarctic Ozone Experiment
- AASE: Airborne Arctic Stratospheric Expedition
- AASE II: Airborne Arctic Stratospheric Expedition II
- Aberporth High Resolution Radiosonde Data
- ACSOE: Atmospheric Chemistry Studies in the Ocean Environment

- ASHOE: Airborne Southern Hemisphere Ozone Experiment
- CIRA: Cospar International Reference Atmosphere
- CLAES: Cryogenic Limb Array Etalon Spectrometer
- CLIM: Climate Station Data
- EAAM: Effective Atmosphere Angular Momentum
- EASOE: European Arctic Stratosphere Ozone Experiment
- ECMWF: Operational Analyses
- ECMWF: Trajectories
- ERA: ECMWF Re-Analysis project
- GEDEX: Greenhouse Effect Detection Experiment
- GOSTA: Global Ocean Temperature Atlas
- HALOE: Halogen Occultation Experiment
- HYREN: Hydrological Radar Experiment
- ISAMS: Improved Stratospheric and Mesospheric Sounder
- LIMS: Limb Infra-Red Monitor of the Stratosphere
- MLS: Microwave Limb Sounder
- MST: Mesosphere Stratosphere Troposphere Radar
- RAD: Radiosonde Data
- SAM II: Stratospheric Aerosol Measurement II
- SAMS: Stratosphere and Mesosphere Sounder
- SPADE: Stratosphere Photochemistry, Aerosols and Dynamics Expedition
- SRB: Surface Radiation Budget
- STEP: Stratosphere-Troposphere Exchange Project
- SYNOP: Synoptic Station Data
- TOMS: Total Ozone Mapping Spectrometer
- TOVS UKMO Analyses: Tiros Operational Vertical Sounder Analyses
- UKMO UARS Assimilated Data

BADC CONTACTS

British Atmospheric Data Centre
Rutherford Appleton Laboratory
Chilton
Didcot
Oxfordshire
OX11 0QX

Telephone: +44 (0) 1235 446432
Fax: +44 (0) 1235 445848
e-mail: badc@rl.ac.uk
Home page: <http://www.badc.rl.ac.uk/>

List of all datasets held at the BADC

Online CD-ROM VHS Video

Not Available Anonymously; BADC Account Required

- AAOE: Airborne Antarctic Ozone Experiment

Measurements from a NASA aircraft campaign to study chemical composition and physical parameters in the Antarctic during the development of the Antarctic Ozone Hole in August and September 1987. The data include atmospheric composition from a variety of instruments, meteorological parameters, aerosol and cloud data.

NATIONAL GEOSCIENCES INFORMATION SERVICE (NGIS)

The National Geosciences Information Service (NGIS) is operated by the British Geological Survey and is the focus and repository for the majority of the nation's geosciences data and information. It represents the public interface to the Survey's data resources and expertise, and it is responsible for the provision of advice on geological matters and for the dissemination of data in forms meaningful and relevant to end users.

STANDARD NGIS DIGITAL DATA PRODUCTS

British Borehole Catalogue **CD ROM**

This catalogue provides an index to over 550 000 boreholes and wells across Britain held in the Survey's National Geological Records Centre. The index can be searched by OS map background or gazetteer and provides details of the position, depth, reference and status of each borehole. It is published in conjunction with GeoInformation International and incorporates ArcView Publisher viewing software to run on a Windows based PC.

Interactive Geoscience Atlas: The Lake District and Adjacent areas **CD ROM**

This multimedia application is based on digital geochemical and geological maps from the Lake District geochemical atlas. These are linked, via icons and a menu system to geophysical and Landsat images. In addition enhanced digital pictures of scenery, geological features, mines, quarries, fossils, mineral specimens, rock thin sections and paleo-environment models are included. Versions are available to run on PC DOS/Windows or Apple Macintosh systems.

Tectonic Map of Britain, Ireland and adjacent areas

This dataset has been generated from a database of separate files, compiled at a 1:1 000 000-scale, comprising pre-Quaternary solid geology, tectonic linework, ornaments and text labels. The tectonic linework file is structured so that the different ages and categories of structure can be readily extracted. It can be provided in a range of vector formats for loading into a user's GIS. The map has been compiled as a collaborative venture with the Geological Survey of Ireland and has also been released in simplified form as a lithoprinted edition.

Geological Maps of United Kingdom

Digital versions of the 1:625 000-scale solid and Quaternary geology maps and the 1:250 000-scale solid geology map series (onshore geology) can be supplied as complete data sets in a range of raster or vector formats. These data sets can be directly loaded into a user's GIS, or can be used to produce customised maps.

NGIS DATA HOLDINGS

Since 1835 BGS has been involved in the creation of a National Archive of geological information for strategic and research purposes. Statutory regulations have ensured the deposition of large quantities of sub-surface information as of right. Exchange agreements have also added much reference material, especially from overseas. Today these collections represent one of the world's largest databases of geoscientific materials.

Data sets for the following areas are available:

World	England & Wales
World Land Areas	Continental Shelf, Offshore
Northwest Europe	Africa
Northwest European Continental Shelf	Bolivia
British Isles	Burma
United Kingdom	Cyprus
Great Britain	Indonesia
England	Kenya
Scotland	Malaysia
Wales	Peru
Northern Ireland	Thailand

The data relate to:

geology: general; boreholes; maps; reports; samples;
biostratigraphy: marine; sedimentology.
geophysics: general; maps; minerals; samples;
geomagnetism: geothermal; marine; remote-sensing;
seismology (earthquakes and profiles)
geophysics: general; maps; minerals; analytical;
mineralogy; petrology
geotechnology: general; maps; reports; engineering
geology; hydrogeology; mining
geography
bibliography

The indexes can be accessed via the World Wide Web. They can be searched *by area:*

UK

- 1:250K Series Land & Offshore Geology Maps
- Aeromagnetic Survey data for UK land areas (with some sea areas).
- Average heights Digital Terrain Model for 1km squares for UK
- BGS Archives (administrative and scientific records, including field notebooks)
- BGS Deep Seismic Data
- BGS Marine Boreholes - offshore borehole material.
- BGS Marine shallow cores
- BGS Seismology archives
- BGS Slide Collection
- BGS photographs of geological interest
- BGS sea-bed sediment samples and splits
- BRITPITS List of UK Mineral Workings (quarries etc).
- Boreholes drilled by BGS IMAU (Industrial Minerals Assessment Unit)

or by topic:

The BGS Data Catalogue - List of Subject Topics

Datasets for the following topics are available:-

- .. GEOLOGY/GENERAL
- 1 GEOLOGY/GENERAL/Boreholes
- 2 GEOLOGY/GENERAL/Maps
- 3 GEOLOGY/GENERAL/Reports
- 4 GEOLOGY/GENERAL/Samples
- 5 GEOLOGY/BIOSTRATIGRAPHY
- 6 GEOLOGY/MARINE
- 7 GEOLOGY/SEDIMENTOLOGY
- 8 GEOPHYSICS/GENERAL

The following example illustrates the level of detail held on individual data sets within the WWW catalogue:

02-Feb-1995	BGS Data Catalogue	Public Datasets
	GEOLOGY/General/Boreholes	
Ref. No.	789	
Title	Index database to BGS borehole records Contains key to other related borehole data.	
Area	UK (Ilands)	
Head at	Keyworth	
Access	Publicly available with restrictions (confidential records must not be shown to public)	
Volume	Over 100,000 records	
Status	Active	
Computer system(s)	VAX	
Software	CAALIS	
Digital data format(s)	ASCII	
Digital media		
Digital media _qualifier(s)		
Non-digital media		
Non-digital media _qualifier(s)		

Digital Data

A wide range of digital data is available under licence from BGS. Typical digital products include:

Raster-scanned and vectorised, fully attributed geological maps at small scales (1:250 000 and 1:625 000), medium scale (1:50 000) and large scale (1:10 000)

Multi-element analyses of stream sediments, soils, heavy mineral pan concentrates and stream waters from the UK 'Geochemical Survey Programme'

Multi-element analyses of rocks, drill core, soils and stream sediments from the UK 'Mineral Reconnaissance Programme'

World Mineral Statistical Database (detailing world-wide production, consumption and trade in minerals)

BGS marine gravity data for the UK continental shelf

BGS gravity data for onshore UK

BGS aeromagnetic data covering the entire UK land area

Aeromagnetic data for the North Sea

Data at one-minute resolution from three UK magnetic observatories available next day

Access to the Library OPAC listing its holdings, including BGS publications, external publications by staff, and many unpublished open-file reports and maps can be made via Telnet and WWW. Alternatively it can be accessed directly via JANET.

CONTACTS

Central Enquiries Officer
National Geosciences Information Service
British Geological Survey
Keyworth
Nottingham NG12 5GG
United Kingdom

Telephone: +44 (0) 115 936 3140

Fax: +44 (0) 115 936 3276

e-mail: ngis@bgs.ac.uk

Home page:

<http://www.nkw.ac.uk/bgs/w3/iserg/ngiswww.html>

NATIONAL WATER ARCHIVE (NWA)

The National Water Archive is maintained by the Institute of Hydrology at Wallingford (UK), a component institute of NERC's Centre for Ecology and Hydrology. A broad range of hydrological - and related - data are being assimilated into the coordinated management provided by the NWA. Data holdings range from the catchment scale, eg detailed climatological and hydrological data for a network of experimental catchments, to national river flow data and DTM and international coverage (world's flood archive).

PUBLICATIONS: THE HYDROLOGICAL DATA UK SERIES

The Hydrological Data UK series of publications is a series of Yearbooks and reports relating to nationally archived hydrological data. The objective of the series is to furnish the data necessary to document year-on-year variations in hydrological conditions and water resources and provide authoritative interpretation of significant trends and hydrological events. Component publications include:

Yearbooks

Each Yearbook brings together the principal data sets relating to river flow, groundwater levels and areal rainfall for the United Kingdom; also tabulated are water quality data for a representative selection of monitoring sites. A comprehensive hydrological review of the year is included together with, when appropriate, feature articles describing noteworthy events or hydrometric developments. The 1995 Yearbook, published in December 1996, is the last hard copy version, bringing to an end the III series from 1981. Elements of the yearbooks (representative river flow and groundwater datasets, annual summaries of hydrological conditions) will be featured on the World Wide Web.

Hydrometric Register and Statistics volumes

These companion publications to the Yearbooks are published in a 5-year cycle. They provide detailed statistical information relating to the featured 5-year period and are a reference source for hydrometric data which does not change materially from year to year. The edition covering the period 1986-90 includes maps, tables and statistics for over 1000 river basins and 150 representative observation boreholes throughout the UK. Publication of the 1991-95 edition is scheduled for 1997.

Reports on notable hydrological events

Occasional reports in the Hydrological Data UK series are prepared to mark outstanding hydrological events. The latest of these examines the 1988-92 drought in a water resources framework and establishes an important benchmark against which future periods of protracted rainfall deficiency may be compared.

Hydrological Monitoring

The Institute of Hydrology and British Geological Survey jointly operate a national hydrological monitoring programme on behalf of Government and the Environment Agencies of Great Britain. Hydrological data are routinely supplied by a number of regional and national authorities concerned with the measurement of hydrometric variables. Data held on the National River Flow Archive and National Groundwater Level Archive provide the necessary historical perspective within which the severity of drought or flood episodes can be assessed. As part of the monitoring programme, reports on rainfall, river flows, groundwater levels and reservoir contents are published monthly (by the tenth working day). These Hydrological Summaries for Great Britain - typically 14 pages in length - form the basis of a range of briefing notes, articles and technical papers aimed at increasing scientific and public awareness of hydrological and water resources issues.

NWA DATA HOLDINGS

The principal datasets fall into two general categories: time series and spatial. Examples of major data holdings appear below.

Time Series

National River Flow Archive
National Groundwater Level Archive
Flood Event Archive
Monthly Catchment Rainfall
FRIEND European Flow Database
World Floods Dataset
Automatic Weather Station data
Soil moisture content databank
Floods Peaks-over-a-threshold Archive

Spatial Data Sets

Digitised Rivers at 1:50 000 and 1:250 000
Digital Terrain Model of the UK
Hydrology of Soil Types map (1km grid)
Digital representation of average rainfall and evaporation
Flood Studies Report Maps
FRIEND European Climate and catchment characteristics
100 year flood risk map of England and Wales (FLOODLANDS)
Vector catchment boundaries

Access arrangements vary between datasets.

The National River Flow Archive (NRFA)

The exploitation and management of water resources and river systems depends to a considerable degree on the ready availability of hydrological data. To service a very broadly-based need for river flow data the UK maintains a

network of over 1200 gauging stations. The relatively dense network is a necessary response to the heterogeneity of the UK in terms of its climate, geology, land use and patterns of water utilisation.

Some gauging stations are maintained by the Institute of Hydrology in their experimental catchments but most flow measurement is undertaken by the Environment Agency in England and Wales and by the Scottish Environment Protection Agency in Scotland; the Departments of Agriculture and Environment undertake a joint operation in Northern Ireland.

The NREA currently holds over 30 000 station years of daily and monthly river flow data together with monthly peak flows and catchment rainfall totals. For a few strategically important catchments naturalised flows (ie adjusted to take account of the net effect of upstream abstractions and discharges) are also archived.

NREA data are published in the Hydrological Data UK series of Yearbooks and reports, and made available through a comprehensive retrieval service with a wide selection of standard retrieval options, which include:

- Tables of daily mean flows (gauged or naturalised)
- Hydrographs of daily or monthly mean flows

- Tables of monthly extreme flows
- Flow duration statistics
- Catchment monthly rainfall and runoff totals
- Running mean plots of annual maximum or minimum flows for selected gauging stations

Further details are given on the World Wide Web and in the Hydrological Data UK series of Publications. Potential users are invited to contact the NWA to discuss the facilities available and their particular needs.

NWA CONTACTS

Requests for any NWA data, and enquiries about the NWA retrieval service should be directed to:

The National Water Archive Office
 Institute of Hydrology
 Wallingford
 Oxfordshire
 OX10 8BB

Telephone: +44 (0) 1491 838800
 Fax: +44 (0) 1491 692424
 e-mail: nwamail@ioh.ac.uk
 Home page: <http://www.nwl.ac.uk/~nrfadata/nwa.html>

A guide to the variation in overall reservoir stocks for England and Wales

A comparison between overall reservoir stocks for England and Wales in recent years

ENVIRONMENTAL INFORMATION CENTRE (EIC)

EIC is hosted by the Institute of Terrestrial Ecology at Monks Wood in Cambridgeshire, a component institute of NERC's Centre for Ecology and Hydrology. The EIC sits at the hub of a distributed data network of regional centres and data managers throughout each of the six ITE research stations. In addition to its role as NERC's Designated Data Centre responsible for terrestrial and freshwater ecological data, EIC takes a leading part in many data-centred programmes of cross-disciplinary research for both European and UK government agencies and commercial companies. It has strong links with UK and European universities, carrying out collaborative research programmes, and providing student placements at both undergraduate and post-graduate levels.

STANDARD EIC PRODUCTS AVAILABLE ON DISKETTE

CIS: Countryside Information System

The CIS is a Microsoft Windows-based software program developed to give policy advisors, planners, researchers, students and teachers easy access to information about the British countryside. Commissioned by the UK's Department of the Environment, the CIS includes a wide range of environmental data - including landscape features, vegetation, habitats and topography - for each square on a one kilometre grid of Great Britain. Further information about CIS can be obtained from the World Wide Web.

CIS: Environmental Catalogue

The CIS Environmental Catalogue is a Microsoft Windows-based hypertext database that provides all the necessary information required to allow users of the CIS to identify and obtain data sets available in CIS format. The catalogue describes all the data sets available, and provides information on the original surveys and definitions, and details of the data suppliers.

EIC DATA HOLDINGS

The Centre maintains an extensive range of data sets which can be made available to enquirers. An index of data sets is available and can be accessed via the World Wide Web. The following list provides information on some of the major data holdings:

Database of the Biological Records Centre

The Biological Records Centre (BRC), a component of EIC, is the UK's national biodiversity data centre. The BRC database comprises about six million records of the distributions of over 15 000 biological species in the British Isles. The majority of the data are donated by volunteer recorders and are received through national recording schemes managed by the BRC. The database is

used to publish distribution atlases and to provide computerised retrieval and mapping services.

CORINE Biotopes Inventory

The database is a computerised inventory of sites of international importance for nature conservation in 13 member states of the European Union (EU). It is currently being extended to other countries in central and eastern Europe. Records identify the location and extent of over 7000 sites, with descriptions of important habitats and biological species, rationale for notification and protection status. The inventory forms a layer of the European Union CORINE GIS on the state of the environment of the EU, co-ordinated by the European Environment Agency (EEA).

Database of Critical Loads of Atmospheric Pollutants

The database comprises estimates of the sensitivity of the land surface of Great Britain to the effects of atmospheric pollution (particularly acid deposition), on the basis of air quality and the sensitivity of receptor soils, geology, freshwaters and vegetation (trees, semi-natural vegetation and crops). The database is managed by the Critical Loads Mapping and Data Centre (MADC) at the EIC and acts as the UK National Focal Centre for the Critical Loads Advisory Group (CLAG) which was set up in 1991 by the Department of the Environment to develop a national critical loads and levels programme.

Ecological Surveys of Great Britain (Countryside Survey)

The database includes information collected in field surveys of selected 1 km squares of the British National Grid, representative of 32 distinct Land Classes (classified according to environmental characteristics such as geology, altitude and climate derived from maps). Information includes botanical data (occurrence and cover within experimental quadrats), soil type and strata, and land cover, and the data have been collected from up to 508 sample squares, surveyed in 1978, 1984 and 1990. The data are regarded as being representative of the land classes and, by classifying every 1 km square of the National Grid, it is possible to make statistical predictions of its probable ecological characteristics.

The Land Cover Map of Great Britain

The Land Cover Map is a digital map derived from the classification of cloud-free satellite images from the American Landsat Thematic Mapper (TM). Produced by the EIC's Remote Sensing Unit, the map identifies 25 land cover types, which include built up areas, arable farm land, pastures and forestry, together with a variety of semi-natural vegetation types. The classes are mapped on a 25 metre raster overlay on the British National Grid to cover the complete land surface of Great Britain.

Database of the NERC United Kingdom Environmental Change Network

The Environmental Change Network (ECN) is a multi-agency, long-term monitoring programme for identifying and quantifying environmental changes associated with man's activities. Hosted by ITE's research station at Merlewood in Cumbria, measurements are collected regularly at a growing number of network sites (currently 10 terrestrial and 37 freshwater) throughout the UK, using standardized protocols. The data cover a wide range of physical, chemical and biological parameters including climate, air quality, water quality and flow, soil development and chemistry, invertebrates, vertebrates, vegetation, land use and site management practice.

Further information about ECN data can be obtained from the World Wide Web at

<http://www.nmw.ac.uk/ecn/index.html>

Analytical Chemistry Databases

The databases are maintained by the Analytical Sections of ITE research stations at Monks Wood and Merlewood, and include the results of over 300 000 biological samples that have been analysed for over 2 million individual determinations. The majority of the Merlewood data relates to water, soil and vegetation analyses for major and minor nutrient and trace elements and the major ions. The Monks Wood data relate to pesticide and toxic

chemical residues in both vertebrate and invertebrate tissue, soils, water and vegetation.

CURRENT EIC PROJECTS

Major programmes and projects with which EIC is involved:

- CEO Centre for Earth Observation
- CIS Countryside Information System
- CS2000 Countryside Survey 2000
- ECN The NERC Environmental Change Network
- ED The NERC Environmental Diagnostics Programme
- EIONET European Environment Information and Observation Network
- FP4 The European Fourth Framework Programme
- LINK British National Space Centre Earth Observation LINK programme
- LOIS The NERC Land Ocean Interaction Study
- TIGER The NERC Terrestrial Initiative in Global Environmental Research
- UNECE United Nations Economic Commission for Europe
- UNEP United Nations Environment Programme

EIC CONTACTS

Database Manager
Environmental Information Centre
Institute of Terrestrial Ecology
Monks Wood
Abbots Ripton
Huntingdon, Cambs. PE17 2LS
United Kingdom

Telephone: +44 (0) 1487 773381

Fax: +44 (0) 1487 773467

e-mail: eic@ite.ac.uk

Home page: <http://www.nmw.ac.uk/ite/eic1.html>

ANTARCTIC ENVIRONMENTAL DATA CENTRE (AEDC)

The Antarctic Environmental Data Centre is the NERC Designated Data Centre for Antarctic data and is located within the British Antarctic Survey (BAS). The AEDC is a 'virtual' data centre providing a gateway to the distributed data holdings of the British Antarctic Survey. It is responsible for ensuring the secure, long term management of BAS data holdings which are individually managed by Principal Investigators and Programme Data Managers.

STANDARD BAS DATA PRODUCTS

The majority of data held by BAS are to support its science programmes. However, a number of standard data products and data resources are available. These include:

Maps of the Antarctic and Antarctica

The BAS Mapping and Geographic Information Centre (MAGIC) produces a range of maps of the Antarctic, including:

- ◆ Topographic and Satellite Image Maps (1: 500 000 and 1: 250 000 scale)
- ◆ Topographic Maps (1: 200 000 scale)
- ◆ Large scale Topographic Maps (Various scales)
- ◆ Geoscience Maps (1: 500 000 and various other scales)
- ◆ BAS GEOMAP series (Various scales)
- ◆ South Georgia Maps (Various Scales)

The BAS on-line map catalogue on the WWW gives further information.

Antarctic Digital Database

The Antarctic Digital Database (ADD) is the product of an international collaborative project, co-ordinated in the UK by BAS, (through its Mapping and Geographic Information Centre), Scott Polar Research Institute and World Conservation Monitoring Centre under the auspices of the Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research and its Working Group on Geodesy and Geographic Information. It represents a major development in Antarctic mapping, providing access to the first seamless digital map of Antarctica, with the most up-to-date and complete coastline of the continent now available in digital form. The database has been prepared from cartographic material published by 11 nations, updated with reference to satellite imagery. Argentina, Australia, China, Germany, New Zealand, Norway, Poland and the UK provided digital data and Japan, Russia and the USA gave permission for their maps to be digitised. The ADD provides the common framework to which multidisciplinary data sets can be referred for GIS applications, facilitating retrieval and evaluation of all data, particularly for monitoring environmental changes in Antarctica. The ADD will evolve to meet the geographical data needs of the international Antarctic scientific community and of programme managers.

Meteorological Data

Historical and current meteorological data are available from BAS, and other, stations. They include monthly mean temperature, pressure, total cloud amount and wind speed (knots) data for Faraday (from 1944 to 1995), Halley (from 1956), Rothera (from 1946) and Signy (from 1947). There are also monthly averages of daily max/min temperatures available for Halley and Rothera. Current station data from the Global Telecommunications System, decoded, are available for all Antarctic stations. These are available about 2 days behind real time in order to pick up late reports. The latest report from each station (decoded about every hour) is available for ships and for land stations.

Data and Biological Resources Centre

The centre contains a large, and unique, collection of plant, invertebrate and microbial specimens (mainly preserved, but some in culture) from Antarctic and Sub-antarctic regions. In addition to the specimens, the Centre holds physical and chemical data for soils and freshwater, microclimate and bibliographic data. The Resource Centre also houses the British Antarctic Survey herbarium (international code AAS) which contains a large collection of plant specimens (over 38 000) from Antarctica, the sub-Antarctic Islands and surrounding continents (especially Fuegia and Patagonia). Over 2000 taxa are represented, comprising predominantly bryophytes and lichens with smaller collections of vascular plants, macro-algae and macro-fungi. The herbarium includes a large literature collection on the taxonomy and distribution of relevant species and a number of useful bibliographic databases.

BIOMASS

The AEDC holds the master copy of the BIOMASS Data Set. BIOMASS (Biological Investigations of Marine Antarctic Systems and Stocks) was a major multi-national scientific programme for the study of the Antarctic marine ecosystem and its living resources, with emphasis on krill (*Euphausia superba*). Data were collected by 34 vessels from 13 countries during 3 field experiments: The First International BIOMASS Experiment (FIBEX), November 1980 to April 1981; The Second International BIOMASS Experiment (SIBEX), Part 1, October 1983 to April 1984 and Part 2, November 1984 to April 1985. The aim of FIBEX was to carry out a quasi-synoptic survey over a wide area of the South Atlantic, Indian Ocean and Pacific sectors of the Southern Ocean. SIBEX 1 & 2 were designed to produce a temporal sequence of observations focused on much smaller areas of the Bransfield Strait and Prydz Bay regions. Data were collected on krill distribution from acoustic surveys and krill population structure from net-hauls. Supporting data from ichthyoplankton net-hauls, oceanographic stations (temperature, salinity, nutrients and chlorophyll-a) and observations of sea-birds at sea were also collected.

BAS DATA HOLDINGS

BAS holds and collects data in support of its scientific programmes, which are currently as follows:

Ice, Climate and Global Change studies the present behaviour of the ice-atmosphere-ocean system in Antarctica and its evolution in the past, and predicts its future behaviour.

Antarctic Palaeoenvironmental Change constructs a picture of changing environments in Antarctica over the past 90 million years from the study of sedimentary and volcanic rocks, ocean sediments and the fossil animals and plants of the region.

Continental Break-up addresses the fundamental scientific problem of why super-continents periodically disintegrate, by developing Gondwana break-up models and studying relationships between active margin tectonics, mantle plumes and continental break-up.

Active Plate Margins studies the generation of continental crust and the main forces responsible for driving and resisting plate motions in two outstanding areas of active plate margins.

Pelagic Ecosystem Studies obtains a quantitative understanding of the major physical-biological interactions occurring within the ecosystem of the Atlantic sector of the Southern Ocean, with particular interest in the role of variability.

Higher Predator Studies investigates the role of seabirds and seals as top predators in the Southern Ocean food web in terms of both nutrient and energy flux and their interactions with commercially exploitable resources.

Ecological and Physiological Adaptations distinguishes the differing effects of temperature and food supply on the ecology and evolution of organisms living in the nearshore marine environment of the Southern Ocean.

Survival Strategies examines survival strategies in representative species from isolated, species-poor polar communities subjected to extremes of temperature, water stress, nutrient and light limitation, and increasing ultraviolet radiation.

Ecosystems and Environmental Change describes the evolution of selected Antarctic terrestrial and freshwater communities, assesses their response and resilience to environmental change and predicts future trends.

Solar Wind-Magnetosphere-Ionosphere Transfer of Energy studies the coupling between the solar wind and magnetosphere; and how, where and how much of the energy, thus transferred in the form of electromagnetic radiation and plasma, reaches the polar ionosphere.

Wave Generation and Propagation studies the processes involved in wave generation and propagation and their role in the overall behaviour of geospace as a coupled system.

Thermosphere-Ionosphere-Mesosphere Aeronomy studies the dissipation of energy in the polar thermosphere, its transport to lower latitudes and coupling to lower altitudes.

The AEDC provides a gateway to the distributed data holdings from these programmes and should be contacted for further information about the scope and availability of data. BAS is currently developing a web based, public access data directory system as part of its Meta Data Management System project, which will give detailed information on BAS's publicly available data sets.

CURRENT AEDC PROJECTS

The AEDC is currently working in 3 main areas as part of its remit to ensure the secure, long term management of BAS data holdings.

1. Developing the BAS Meta Data Management System, to provide Principal Investigators and Data Managers with a facility to enable the systematic recording and management of a standardised set of meta data, or information about data.
2. Developing guidelines of good practice for the management of data and reviewing the processes used to manage data against these guidelines, to identify strengths and weaknesses, by means of a Data Management Process Audit.
3. Providing advice on data storage mechanisms and media to ensure the long term availability of BAS's data holdings. This includes the implementation of a centralised BAS Data Storage Facility, for the secure long term storage of primary copies of all BAS data sets.

In addition, as one of the National Antarctic Data Centres within the International Antarctic Data Directory System it is playing a key role in defining standards and procedures for the definition and management of Antarctic meta data and Antarctic data catalogues.

AEDC CONTACTS

Antarctic Environmental Data Centre
British Antarctic Survey
High Cross, Madingley Road
Cambridge CB3 0ET

Telephone: +44 (0) 1223 251400

Facsimile: +44 (0) 1223 362616

e-mail: aedc@bas.ac.uk

Home page: <http://www.nerc-bas.ac.uk/public/aedc/>

NERC SCIENTIFIC SERVICES DATA CENTRE (NSSDC)

The NERC Scientific Services Data Centre (NSSDC) is based at NERC Swindon Office. It is the Designated Data Centre with responsibility for NERC holdings of data that are not discipline related, notably remotely sensed imagery from satellites and aircraft.

ASSOCIATED DATA HOLDINGS

NERC holds three main categories of remotely sensed Earth observation data, viz

- ◆ The Dundee Satellite Receiving Station Archive
- ◆ Remotely sensed imagery acquired by NERC's own aircraft
- ◆ An image archive of satellite data acquired by NERC from commercial sources, which for copyright reasons can be made available to NERC staff and NERC-supported members of the academic community only.

NERC Scientific Services provides value-added products, such as sea-surface temperature data, derived from imagery received at Dundee, as a service in near real-time.

NERC also holds an archive of air photography acquired during its Airborne Remote Sensing campaigns.

Various services and facilities supported by NERC Scientific Services have collections of data which are available on application direct to the facility or to the appropriate Designated Data Centre.

The Dundee Satellite Receiving Station Archive

The Dundee Satellite Receiving Station (DSRS) has been continuously receiving and archiving data from meteorological satellites (AVHRR and TOVS) since 1976. DSRS holds a complete archive of all raw data back to October 1978. In addition, there are Coastal Zone Colour Scanner (CZCS) data from the NOAA NIMBUS 7 satellite. The digital data are complemented by browse files of quick-look infra-red and visual images. Quick-look browse file images from all five channels of AVHRR can be viewed on the World Wide Web.

For further information contact URL
<http://www.sat.dundee.ac.uk/>

The NERC Airborne Remote Sensing Archive

There is a large archive of NERC airborne campaign data (1982 to present), where the holdings are mainly Airborne Thematic Mapper (ATM) data, with a growing holding of hyperspectral sensor data from a Compact Airborne Spectrographic Imager (*casid*).

The NERC Image Archive

NSSDC administers a central archive and catalogue of satellite data. It will undertake data availability searches from internal and external archives on behalf of the NERC-funded community. The Data Centre holds a modest budget for new acquisitions in support of NERC programmes and will order data for the NERC community. Such central purchasing aims at avoiding replication of purchase and ensures custodianship of valuable data. The Data Centre will also provide advice on copyright regulations pertaining to the use of commercial satellite data.

The Image Archive contains some 2000 reels of tape holding commercial satellite data. There is total UK coverage of Landsat Thematic Mapper (TM) and Multispectral Scanner (MSS) scenes, supplemented by a small SPOT archive and minor holdings of a range of experimental sensors. There is also a less extensive archive of overseas scenes, the majority of the holdings being in Africa, Europe and Antarctica.

Air photography and Ancillary data

Additionally, the NSSDC holds the master archive of film negatives from the NERC airborne campaign photography, together with all ancillary information allied to the campaigns (maps, annual flying reports, calibration information etc).

Further information is held on the WWW at URL
<http://www.nerc.ac.uk/nssdata.htm>

The NERC Remote Sensing Data Analysis Service

The Remote Sensing Data Analysis Service, based at the Plymouth Marine Laboratory, provides processed products from the AVHRR satellite data received at Dundee, for use by environmental scientists who are not specialists in remote sensing, or do not have access to image analysis hardware or software.

Further information is held on the WWW at URL
<http://www.npm.ac.uk/rsdas/>

Other NERC Scientific Services Data

The Mesosphere Stratosphere and Troposphere Radar (MST Radar) facility data are held at the British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC), qv.

Further information is held on the WWW at URL
<http://www.badc.rl.ac.uk/>

The NERC Radiocarbon Laboratory holds age reports in the RCL databank, from where they are available for general access, normally after a minimum period of 18 months. A CD-ROM containing RCL age reports for the period 1977-1988 is to be published shortly.

NSS DATA CENTRE CONTACTS

NERC Scientific Services Data Centre
c/o Polaris House
North Star Avenue
Swindon
Wiltshire SN2 1EU

Telephone: +44 (0) 1793 411955
Fax: +44 (0) 1793 411959
e-mail: data@nss.nerc.ac.uk
Home page: <http://www.nerc.ac.uk/nssdata.html>

Dundee Satellite Receiving Station
Dept of Applied Physics & Electronic & Manufacturing
Engineering
Dundee DD1 4HN

Telephone: +44 (0) 1382 344406
Fax: +44 (0) 1382 202575
e-mail: peb@sat.dundee.ac.uk
Home page: <http://www.sat.dundee.ac.uk/>

Remote Sensing Data Analysis Service
c/o Plymouth Marine Laboratory
Prospect Place
West Hoe
Plymouth
Devon PL1 8AA

Telephone: +44 (0) 1752 633150
Fax: +44 (0) 1752 666101
e-mail: s.groom@nss.nerc.ac.uk
Home page: <http://www.npm.ac.uk/rsdas/>

Phytoplankton bloom in the north east Atlantic: this image was created by RSDAS at Plymouth from satellite data received at Dundee, and transmitted to a research vessel sampling in the area.

NSSDC holds the archive of imagery and photography acquired by NERC's aircraft.

NERC Designated Data Centres

Further information about NERC's Designated Data Centres can be obtained from the NERC World Wide Web home page URL <http://www.nerc.ac.uk/>

Antarctic Environmental Data Centre

British Antarctic Survey
High Cross
Madingley Road
Cambridge
CB3 0ET

Telephone: +44 (0) 1223 251400
Facsimile: +44 (0) 1223 362616
e-mail: aedc@bas.ac.uk
Home page: <http://www.nerc-bas.ac.uk/public/aedc/>

British Atmospheric Data Centre

Rutherford Appleton Laboratory
Chilton
Didcot
Oxfordshire
OX11 0QX

Telephone: +44 (0) 1235 446432
Fax: +44 (0) 1235 445848
e-mail: badc@rl.ac.uk
Home page: <http://www.badc.rl.ac.uk/>

British Oceanographic Data Centre

Proudman Oceanographic Laboratory
Bidston Observatory
Birkenhead
Merseyside
L43 7RA

Telephone: +44 (0) 151 653 8633
Fax: +44 (0) 151 652 3950
e-mail: bodcmail@pol.ac.uk
Home page: <http://www.nbi.ac.uk/bodc/bodcmain.html>

Environmental Information Centre

Institute of Terrestrial Ecology
Monks Wood
Abbots Ripton
Huntingdon
Cambs
PE17 2LS

Telephone: +44 (0) 1487 773381
Fax: +44 (0) 1487 773467
e-mail: eic@ite.ac.uk
Home page: <http://www.nmw.ac.uk/ite/eic1.html>

National Geosciences Information Service

British Geological Survey
Keyworth
Nottingham
NG12 5GG

Telephone: +44 (0) 115 936 3140
Fax: +44 (0) 115 936 3276
e-mail: ngis@bgs.ac.uk
Home page: <http://www.nkw.ac.uk/bgs/w3/iser/ngiswww.html>

The National Water Archive

Institute of Hydrology
Wallingford
Oxfordshire
OX10 8BB

Telephone: +44 (0) 1491 838800
Fax: +44 (0) 1491 692424
e-mail: nwamail@ioh.ac.uk
Home page: <http://www.nwl.ac.uk/~nrfadata/nwa.html>

NERC Scientific Services Data Centre

c/o Polaris House
North Star Avenue
Swindon
Wiltshire
SN2 1EU

Telephone: +44 (0) 1793 411955
Fax: +44 (0) 1793 411959
e-mail: data@nss.nerc.ac.uk
Home page: <http://www.nerc.ac.uk/nssdata.html>

Compiled by the

NERC Data Strategy Group

c/o Directorate of Science and Technology
Polaris House
North Star Avenue
Swindon
Wiltshire
SN2 1EU

Telephone: +44 (0) 1793 411683
Fax: +44 (0) 1793 411610
e-mail: data-strategy@nerc.ac.uk